

Re: Full Paper

From [Gucin Konuk](#) on 2020-08-22 11:40

[Details](#) [Teks murni](#)

received your papers , before start review need write to you about publishing fee
in fact after fast review (2 week) need pay 400 usd publishing fee after that will be publish less 30 days this is ok ?
please confirm up to start review your paper
best regards

On Wed, 19 Aug 2020 at 09:12, <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id> wrote:

Dear Editor,

I want to publish my article in your journal. Please help so that my article can be published in your journal. thank you

Best Regard
Achmad Faqih

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From [Gucin Konuk](#) on 2020-11-03 15:10

 [Teks murni](#)

received final of your papers +receipt of payment will be send acc letter up to 48 hours to you
this paper will be publish up to 10 dec

On Mon, 2 Nov 2020 at 11:58, <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id> wrote:

Pada 2020-09-22 13:10, Gucin Konuk menulis:

> Dear

> after complete payment will be send acc letter to you

> best regards

>

> On Mon, 21 Sep 2020 at 05:58, <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id> wrote:

>

>> Pada 2020-09-10 15:03, Gucin Konuk menulis:

>>> Dear

>>>

>>> your paper has been accepted ,you can pay payment papers to under

>>> account and format your paper according template and rules and

>> polices

Fwd: Full Paper

From [Gucin Konuk](#) on 2020-11-04 19:00

 [Teks murni](#)

acc letter is attachment
best regards

EurAsian Journal of BioSciences

Eurasia J Biosci

Date: November 4, 2020

Certificate of Acceptance

Title of Paper: FARMER'S PERCEPTION ON RICE FARM INSURANCE PROGRAM

Authors: Achmad Faqih

Dear Authors,

The Editorial Board of **EurAsian Journal of BioSciences (Eurasia J Biosci, e-ISSN 1307-9867)** hereby states with great pleasure that following the reviewing process, your above indicated manuscript has been accepted for publication in issue (2) 2020.

We would like to thank you for your submitted paper.

Regards,

Editor
Yunus Dogan

EurAsian Journal of BioSciences
Turkey

